

Journal of Social and Political Sciences

Vera, Nawiroh, and Azmi, Khaerul. (2019), Effectivity of Communication General Election Commission Tangerang City in Socialization About “Kotak Kosong.” In: *Journal of Social and Political Sciences*, Vol.2, No.2, 260-268.

ISSN 2615-3718

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1991.02.02.67

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

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Effectivity of Communication General Election Commission Tangerang City in Socialization About “Kotak Kosong”

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Abstract

In June 2018 Indonesia conducted the general election of the regional head (pilkada) simultaneously. The interesting thing about pilkada this time is the emergence of the phenomenon of a single candidate in some area. One area that has a single candidate in the city of Tangerang. Voter ballots where there is only a single candidate, the partner is an empty box. Not all societies understand what an empty box is, so socialization is needed for the community to understand. The purpose of this research is to know and analyze the effectiveness of socialization about "empty box" conducted by the General Election Commission (KPU) Tangerang City in Tangerang mayoral election in 2018. This research approach is quantitative. The methods that were used is the survey method with descriptive type. The technique of data retrieval is done through questionnaires distributed to the respondents selected by purposive. The subjects of this study are the people of Tangerang City who have the right to vote which is categorized based on age that is 17 years old until 60 years old. Based on the result of the preliminary survey, it is known that the socialization conducted by KPU-Tangerang has not been effective yet, from 100 respondents obtained 50% result know about the existence of 'kotak kosong' (empty box) while 50% others do not know. Of the respondents who knew about the empty box, 89% were obtained from the Network of Empty Boxes, not from the KPU.

Keywords: Effectiveness, Socialization, General Election Commission (KPU), Empty Box

INTRODUCTION

Elections are a form of political aspiration of the people and the establishment of a democratic milestone. Countries that embrace the democratic system, the general election becomes the main indicator. Democracy in accordance with its meaning is to involve the people actively in determining the direction and political policy of a country.

Indonesia as a democratic country has democratic political consequences that must be implemented. In Indonesia, there are 10 political parties that pass to parliament (kompas.com/2018). Of the ten parties, there are different coalitions in support of candidates in the regional head elections. one of which is the election of the mayor of Tangerang City.

Tangerang mayor candidate is only one partner, Arif Wismansyah and Sachrudin Supported by all parties. This single candidate phenomenon has not been widely known by the Tangerang community as a potential voter. Is the image to be punched just a picture of Arif-Sachrudin's partner? Or there is another picture that can be punched. Because it is the first time, Tangerang people experience such things. For that reason, intensive socialization of the General Election Commission (KPU) of Tangerang City is required to make the democratic party run in accordance with the laws that result in democratic governance.

The duties and working procedures of Commissioner and Secretariat of KPU of Tangerang City are regulated by RI Law Number 15 the Year 2011, regarding the General Election Organizer. Communication between KPU commissioners and various elements of society is needed in order to achieve transparent, accountable, honest election qualities in accordance with the vision and mission and the objectives of democracy. In the implementation of socialization required effective communication.

Communication is said to be effective if people are able to convey what it means. Communication is said to be effective when the stimuli conveyed and intended by the sender or source are closely related to the stimuli captured and understood by the recipient (Mulyana, 2000: 22).

Socialization is the duty and responsibility of KPU as the organizer of the election. Socialization of elections is part of political socialization. According to Tensey & Jackson 2008 Political socialization in the study of political science is actually the same as political education. It is said that because in it there is a broader and more informal understanding, with an emphasis on the importance of its influence, or the power to influence (in Kartika 2016: 47). The political socialization aims to provide political education that shapes and fosters political personality and political awareness, as well as people's political participation. According to Michael Rush and Philip Althoff, political socialization is a process of how to introduce a political system to a person. Not only introduce but also how the person determines his responses and reactions to the existing political phenomena. (in Prihatmoko, 2003: 180).

Socialization is important in order to inform the community about the election procedures, as well as to increase the participation of electoral participants. Communities have the right to channel their voting rights and determine who is worthy of trust in leading the region. Based on the observation of socialization researchers on how to choose if there are only one candidate election participants not yet maximal. This is evidenced by preliminary research on the existence of "*kotak kosong*" (empty box) terms that can also be selected in the general election. Based on interviews that researchers do randomly the results were still many people who do not know about the empty box. The socialization of the "*kotak kosong*" program is actually a program that must be implemented by the KPU if the electoral district has only one candidate pair, but based on the initial survey, the public knows about the empty box from empty boxed network (JKK) which appears spontaneously in socializing the Tangerang City elections 2018 where there is only one single candidate against the "*kotak kosong*".

The Empty Box Network (JKK) is the public response to the phenomenon of the emergence of the Single Candidate Pair in Pemilukada in Tangerang City in 2018. JKK was born on anxiety over the awareness that the election of the Regional Head is a contestation to choose from the many best local sons to be leaders, this is Tangerang City. However, what happened (with a single paslon phenomenon) was not an election, but the people were "forced" to vote because only one Pair of Candidates appeared in the arena of political contestation in Tangerang City. The question asked by the Empty Box Network is whether the appearance of candidate's sole is because of the level of "satisfaction" of society so that society unanimously re-elects *Petahana* (single Paslon), or because there are other things that "hurt democracy." This is what needs a sharper discussion. To explore and search for the "red thread" phenomenon of a single candidate is the Empty Box Network (JKK) born.

Based on the background that has been prepared above it can be drawn identification problems arising from the socialization conducted KPU namely: How effectiveness of communication about the socialization of "kotak kosong" in the community Tangerang City?

The purpose of this study to determine the effectiveness of electoral commissions Tangerang City (KPU) in the socialization of the "kotak kosong" to the community. The significance of this research is to know the effectiveness of communication made by the government in this case the General Elections Commission in conducting socialization as a form of literacy to the public.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Regional elections

The general election of the regional head or commonly abbreviated as *Pemilukada* or *Pilkada* is the general election to elect regional head and deputy regional head directly in Indonesia by the eligible local population (Arbas, 2012: 31). General Regional Election (*Pilkada*) is political recruitment that is the selection of people against the candidates nominating themselves as Regional Head, either Governor / Vice Governor or Regent / Vice Regent or Mayor / Deputy Mayor.

Pilkada is at the same time a process of democracy in which elections are conducted against the regional heads at the provincial, district / city level, within the scope of certain territories undertaken simultaneously throughout Indonesia (<https://www.kajianpustaka.com/2016/11/pemilihan-kepala-daerah-pilkada.htm>).

Empty Box

The "Empty Box" is a consequence of the emergence of the Election Commission Regulation No. 11 of 2016 which regulates the election of a single candidate in *pasal 11A*, which regulates ballot papers in the election of one candidate pair by containing two columns consisting of one column containing photographs and names of candidate pairs and blank columns that are not pictorial or more popular with the term "empty box". PKPU No.8 Year 2017 also further regulates the socialization of "blank column" in the regional general election which is held with one candidate pair.

In the General Election in 2018, there are a total of 16 districts / cities that organize the election of leaders by presenting only one candidate pair. 3 (three) of them are located in the region of Banten, namely Tangerang City, Tangerang Regency and Lebak Regency (<http://proaksi.co.id/2018/06/26/>).

The Concept of Political Socialization

Political socialization and political participation are interrelated concepts. According to Maran (Maran, 2001: 135), the meaning of political socialization is a process that allows an individual can recognize the political system, which then determines the nature of his perceptions about politics and his reactions to political phenomena. Relates to political participation that has individual involvement at various levels in a political system.

The definition of "socialization" in the assessment team of the effectiveness of dissemination of information in the context of socializing new ways of voting in the legislative elections is a mechanism of delivering information on voting procedures to the public or voters through various patterns and forms of activities, either directly or indirectly relate to the public or voting rights owners (Mandagi et al, 2009: 3).

Socialization is considered successful if most of the targeted socialization community understands the content of the message delivered by the socialization officer. If socialization is successful, then communication can be called effective. This study tried to measure how much knowledge of the community about "kotak kosong" so it can also know how effective communication made by the general election commission of Tangerang city in socializing it.

Communication Effectiveness

According to Hardjana (2000: 37), effectiveness is about how the recipient to do something with the desired meaning of the sender of the message. Communication effectiveness is the process of delivering a message that is able to achieve the purpose of the content of the message and provide feedback, or reaction so that the message can be conveyed and generate an effective communication. According to Suranto Aw, communication can be said to be effective if, in a communication process, the message conveyed a communicator can be accepted and understood by the communicant, exactly as the communicator wants. (Suranto, 2005)

It could be said the effective communication if people managed to convey what he meant. This is actually a measure of communication effectiveness. Generally speaking, communication is considered effective when the stimuli conveyed and intended by the sender or source are closely related to the stimuli captured and understood by the recipient.

Stewart L. Tubs and Sylvia Moss (in Rachmat, 2001: 13) say that effective communication has at least five things: understanding, pleasure, influence on attitudes, improved relationships, and actions.

The factors of communication effectiveness are

1. Trust
2. Relationships
3. Satisfaction
4. Clarity
5. Balance and consistency
6. The ability of news recipients
7. News sender channels

(Alfin Ahya, academia.edu)

METHODOLOGY

Types and Research Methods

The type of this research is descriptive with a quantitative approach. According to Rachmat Kriyantono (2010: 50) "Quantitative Research is research that describes or explains a problem that the results can be generalized. Thus no need to emphasize the depth of data or research. Meanwhile, according to Sugiyono (2008: 8) quantitative approach is defined as a research method based on the philosophy of Positivism, used to examine the population and certain samples, data collection using research instruments, quantitative / statistical data analysis with the aim to test the hypothesis set.

This research method is a survey method. "Surveys are a method of research using questionnaires as their data collection instrument." (Kriyantono, 2006: 60). The research process by survey method is a series of steps that are done in a planned and systematic, mutually supportive, and as a whole is a common thread (Elvinaro, 2010: 53). "This type of descriptive survey is used when researchers want to describe a condition in society, rather than finding out the relationship and influence of the two variables." (Kriyantono, 2006: 61).

Subjects and objects of research

The subjects of this study are the people of Tangerang City who have the right to vote which the researcher categorizes based on age that is aged 17 years to 60 years. While the object in this research is the socialization program about "*kotak kosong*" by KPU Tangerang City.

Population and Sample

Population

The population is all parts or all members of the object to be observed or researched. The population may be any person, object, object, event or whatever object of the survey (Elvinaro, 2010: 170). The population in this study

is the population of Tangerang City between the ages of 17 years to 60 years which is the List of Permanent Voters (DPT).

Table 1: The population of Tangerang City is categorized by age and gender

Gender	Age	Population
Male	17-60 years	519.069
female	17-60 years	518.300
	Total	1.037.369

Source: KPU Kota Tangerang

Based on data sources from the Tangerang City KPU, the total population in this study amounted to 1,037,369 people.

Sample

The sample is a collection of research objects only by studying and observing a portion of the collection. The representative part of the population object that we observe is called the sample (Rachmat, 2009: 78). To determine the number of samples used Slovin formula.

$$n = \frac{N}{N(d)^2 + 1}$$

N = population

n = sample

d = precision (degree of accuracy 10%)

1 = constant number

$$n = \frac{1.037.369}{1 + (1.037.369)(0,1)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{1.037.369}{10.374,69}$$

$$n = 99,987$$

Based on the calculation of samples by using Slovin formula obtained results of 99, 987 that researchers rounded to 100. So the sample used in this study as many as 100 people. Sampling technique that researchers use in this study is purposive sampling.

Research Results and discussion

The survey was conducted by spreading the questionnaire through social media and directly to the respondents. One example of a survey through social media as shown below.

Figure 1

Based on the survey results that have been done can be mapped data based on the identity of respondents as follows:

Table 2. Characteristics of Respondents by age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
17-30	30	30%
31-40	25	25%
41-50	31	31%
51-60	14	14%
Total	100	100%

Table 3. Respondent characteristics by sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
female	35	35%
male	65	65%
Total	100	100%

Table 4. Characteristics of respondents by education

Education	Frequency	Percentage
Tidak sekolah	1	1%
SD	4	4%
SMP	21	21%
SMA	52	52%

SARJANA	22	22%
Total	100	100%

Table 5. Characteristics of Respondents by Occupation

Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
Ibu Rumah Tangga	20	20%
PNS	10	10%
Swasta	55	55%
Pelajar/Mahasiswa	15	15%
Total	100	100%

From the collected data, the highest number of respondents is 41-50 years old with 31%, the second largest number of respondents is 17-30 years by 30%. The smallest number of respondents aged 51-60 years is only 14%. Gender data of respondents, male more than female with the highest education level of respondents, are high school graduates by 52% while based on the most work is a private employee of 55%. Interesting to see the data of respondents above, in terms of education level the highest number of high school graduates and the second highest number is Bachelor. A person with high school and college education will be more open in accepting new knowledge, as well as intellectually established.

Communication Effectiveness

Communication is called effective when in a communication process, the message conveyed a communicator can be accepted and understood by the communicant, exactly as the communicator wants. The effectiveness of this research would like to see how the views of respondents to communications conducted KPU Tangerang in disseminating about 'empty box' in the election of Tangerang Mayor in elections 2018. The results of data collection on the effectiveness of respondents are as follows.

Table 6. respondents' knowledge of "kotak kosong."

Statement	Amount	Percentage
Know	50	50%
Do not know	50	50%
Total	100	100%

Table 7. The acquisition of information resources

Statement	Amount	Percentage
general election commission (KPU)	11	11%
empty box network (JKK)	89	89%
Total	100	100%

Based on data collection, it can be seen that Tangerang people who know and do not know about "kotak kosong" in election 2018 balanced with the percentage of 50% know and 50% do not know. Then in the next statement addressed only to respondents who know where they get information about the "kotak kosong." The result was 11% obtained information from the KPU, and 89% obtained information from the Empty Box Network (JKK).

From the preliminary survey result, it can be said that Tangerang KPU is not effective and not maximal in socializing "kotak kosong" to the community. This is proven by most of Tangerang community knowing "kotak kosong" from JKK as Tangerang 2018 election volunteer, not from KPU that should do. The socialization of the election is very important in order to succeed transparent and functional democracy, but the pilkada case in Tangerang is actually JKK which has more role in the socialization of "kotak kosong."

CONCLUSION

From the discussion that has been done in this study can be concluded that communication Commission Election Tangerang in disseminating “*kotak kosong*” can be said not effective. This is evidenced by the distribution of initial questionnaires in Tangerang society. The result shows that the respondents know the existence of “*kotak kosong*” not from the socialization of Tangerang Electoral Commission but from Empty Box Network (JKK) that is 89% of respondents. These results become a reference for researchers to further examine the performance of the Tangerang Election Commission of Tangerang in the 2018 election, whether the task of KPU has been implemented with the maximum or not.

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